

What are the challenges for environmentally friendly delivery in urban outskirts?

SuCoLo is researching sustainable, inner-city delivery options for goods in urban outskirts, in particular through the use of cargo bikes and new digital solutions for *all*, because:

- **More people are moving to small towns:** Big cities and city centers are crowded, so more people are choosing to live in urban outskirts or smaller towns in the near surroundings.
- **Deliveries from online shopping:** Lots of people order things online, which means more deliveries are needed.
- **Deliveries cause pollution:** Delivery vans can dirty the air.
- **Online shopping can be difficult for people with disabilities:** because some people can't see well, can't hear well, have trouble using their hands, need accessible web solutions or assistive tools.

SuCoLo wants to make deliveries easier in 3 ways:

- **Pick-up stations:** SuCoLo will set up special pick-up stations in 3 cities: Leipzig, Merano and Salzburg. People can pick up their deliveries there easily.
- **Cargo bikes:** SuCoLo will also use cargo bikes to deliver things without polluting the air.
- **Accessible for *all*:** SuCoLo will make sure that everyone can use pick-up stations and services, including families, elderly persons and people with disabilities.

What are the biggest challenges in this context?

- **Pick-up stations:** We need to find easy-to-reach places to put the stations.
- **Cargo bikes:** We have to offer special bikes with 3 wheels and electric power that are easy for everyone to use. We need to make sure the roads are safe for cargo bikes and that the cargo bikes can carry enough stuff. In the participating 3 cities there aren't many cargo bikes yet, so SuCoLo wants to make them more popular for green transport, too.
- **Online-Shopping:** SuCoLo has to develop sustainable methods for digital behaviour change.

Finding suitable locations for the pick-up stations!

SuCoLo wants to find the best places to put the pick-up stations so everyone can easily pick up their deliveries! **Here's what we are looking for:**

- **Lots of people nearby:** In a busy area where many people live.
- **Easy to reach:** Not too far away and safely reachable by bike or walking.
- **Accessible for everyone:** Also suitable for families, elderly persons and people with disabilities.
- **Public place:** On public ground, not on someone's private property.
- **Safe from damage:** Locations protected against burglary and theft.

Making pick-up stations accessible for everyone!

SuCoLo wants to make deliveries and bike sharing more accessible for everyone! **Here's what we are considering:**

- **Getting there safely:** Accessible public transport, sidewalks and bike paths to get safely to the pick-up station.
- **Accessibility:** There should be ramps and elevators if needed, wide enough for people with pushchairs, walkers or wheelchairs.
- **Easy to use:** Clear information and signs everyone can understand.

Using cargo bikes and alternative barrier-free mobility aids for *all*

SuCoLo wants to find ways to make deliveries by cargo bikes work better. The approach envisages cargo bikes for delivery services, but also for private customers and businesses. Here are some of the problems:

- **Safety:** Some roads might be too dangerous for cargo bikes.
- **Long distances:** Delivering things can take a long time if the places are far apart.
- **Not everything fits:** Cargo bikes are not able to carry as much stuff as trucks.
- **Bad weather:** Rain or snow can make it dangerous to ride these bikes.
- **People not at home:** If someone isn't at home when the delivery arrives, the bike might have to go back later.

Making deliveries in the 15 minute city greener and easier!

SuCoLo wants to find ways to make deliveries in the 15 minute city greener and easier. **Here's what the 3 participating cities are focusing on:**

- **Leipzig:** SuCoLo is working with stores and a bike delivery company to test behavior changing techniques.
- **Merano:** There are not many stores with online shopping and only one bike delivery company, that's why SuCoLo in Merano is working with traditional shops and cargo bikes to see if these bikes can be used for deliveries.
- **Salzburg:** There are not many stores offering online shopping with bike delivery in Salzburg. SuCoLo is looking for partners to test their ideas.

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